

STATISTICAL OFFICE OF THE REPUBLIC OF SLOVENIA

DwB
Data without Boundaries

Social Science Data Archives

COOPERATION OF AN ARCHIVE AND AN NSI TO ADD VALUE TO DETAILED NON-ANONYMISED MICRODATA

The Slovenian good practice

Sebastian Kočar (Slovene Social Science Data Archives)

5th Conference of the European Survey Research Association – ESRA 2013

Ljubljana, Slovenia

July 2013

The current state of art – issues and solutions

- Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia (SORS) collects a great amount of data
- in theory, registered researchers can access all their official statistics microdata
- the distributed microdata, available in the safe room or by the remote access, are not ready for analysis immediately
- no structured metadata are made available to researchers
- Social Science Data Archives (ADP) can add value to those detailed non-anonymised microdata in cooperation with SORS

An overview of our cooperation in the past

- has been going on since the establishment of the Slovenian Social Science Data Archives (ADP)
- ADP has been distributing anonymised SORS microdata (selection of variables, samples) and structured metadata
- Labour Force Survey, Household Budget Survey, Time Budget Survey, Crime Victim Survey, Census 2002
- less intense cooperation between 2002 and 2011, no newly distributed SORS microdata
- partnership of both organizations in the project since May 2011

DwB as an initiative for increasing the cooperation

- the main goal of the project is to improve the research environment, access to detailed official statistics microdata in Europe
- we recognized the need to concentrate on improving the research environment, access and quality of access to (detailed) official statistics microdata, on the national level
- the products of our work inside of separate work packages could be used in modified form to achieve cooperation goals easier
- without close cooperation with SORS departments, finishing WP5 tasks efficiently would be almost impossible for ADP

The purpose and the aim of our cooperation – ADP's POV

- one of Social Science Data Archives' missions is to provide quality microdata and metadata to different groups of data users: under-graduate students, postgraduate students, young researchers at faculties, research organizations, registered researchers
- by distributing mostly Public Use Files on our webpage, we can't concentrate on the needs of experts in the social sciences field, namely registered researchers and research institutes
- ADP can also help SORS with its experience and expertise in the field - researchers can benefit in the long term

Forms of cooperation

- microdata: intensive work on deindividualized microdata, ready to be used immediately for statistical analysis using preferred software
- microdata: preparing PUF files, later distributed by ADP
- metadata: analysis of possible automatic harvesting
- metadata: preparing structured metadata for researchers
- metadata: counseling on inclusion of DDI standard to SORS procedures
- activities to promote official statistics microdata scientific use, workshops for students

Preparing deindividualized microdata – what we do

- preparing deindividualized microdata in the safe room environment, the same access conditions as for other registered researchers
- SPSS is used, SPSS syntax is written
- variable and value labels, missing values are added to the dataset; additional logical control is made, unneeded variables are deleted, variables in databases are connected to codebooks used
- by using SPSS syntax prepared, microdata can be exported in any desired format, readable by variety of software used by researchers

Preparing deindividualized microdata – how we do it

id	sifra	starost	datum	starost	ank	refced	v1_1	v1_4	v1_5
1	1	8	10	11	11	11	11	11	11
2	2	9	10	11	11	11	11	11	11

+

```

GET DATA
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  /DELIMITER='*'
  /ARRANGEMENT=UNLIMITED
  /FIRSTCASE=2
  /IMPORTCASE=ALL
  /VARIABLES=
    sid A13
    l_sifa A10
    sifa A9
    v1_F10
    datum A10
    starost F2.0
    ank F3.0
    refced F2.0
    v1_1 F1.0
    v1_4 F1.0
    v1_5 F2.0
    v1_7 F1.0
    v1_8 F1.0
    v1_9c F2.0
    v1_10 F1.0
    v1_11a F2.0
    v1_12 F1.0
    v1_13a F2.0
    v1_14 F2.0
    v1_15a F2.0
    v1_16 F1.0
    v1_17 F2.0
    v2_1 F2.0
    v2_2a F4.0
    v1_13a_2
    v1_14 F4.0
    v1_15a F2.0
    v1_16 F1.0
    v1_17 F2.0
    v2_1 F2.0
  /VAR LABELS=
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    l_sifa 'Št. članke'
    sifa 'Št. članke'
    v1_F10 'Št. članke'
    datum 'Datum anketiranja'
    starost 'Starost anketir.'
    ank 'Anketa'
    refced 'Referenčni tedni'
    v1_1 'Ali bo oseba od. (1,00, Da)..'
    v1_4 'Razmerja med .. (1,00, njego..'
    v1_5 'Njegovih par. (1,00, otrok a..'
    v1_6 'Njegovih oča. (1,00, otrok a..'
    v1_7 'Njegova/ena. (1,00, otrok a..'
    v1_8 'Spol. (1,00, mešč..'
    v1_9a 'Dan rojstva'
    v1_9c 'Mesec rojstva'
    v1_10 'Leto rojstva'
    v1_11a 'Ali imate sloven. (1,00, Da)..'
    v1_12 'Ali ste bili rojen. (1,00, Da)..'
    v1_13a 'V kateri državi. (2,00, Se n..'
    v1_14 'Kateroga leta s. (1,00, Omo..'
    v1_15a 'Iz katere države. (1,00, Omo..'
    v1_16 'Ali imate na te. (1,00, stah..'
    v1_17 'Kakšen je vaš. (1,00, Sams..'
    v2_1 'Vaša dosežena. (1,00, ste br..'
    v2_2a 'Kaj ste po izbor. (None, None..'
    v1_13a_2 'Kateroga leta s. (None, None..'
    v1_14 'Ali ste v zadnji. (1,00, Da)..'
    v1_15a 'Katero stopnja. (1,00, Omo..'
    v1_16 'Ali ste v zadnji. (1,00, Da)..'
    v1_17 'Koliko ur ste v. (None, None..'
    v2_1 'Tačaj, seminar. (1,00, potre..'
    v2_2 'Tajnik, strokov. (1,00, potre..'
  /
  
```

=

Name	Type	Width	Decimals	Label	Values	Missing	Columns	Align
sid	Numeric	8	2	Štatskični ident.	None	None	8	Right
l_sifa	Numeric	8	2	Val anketiranja	None	None	8	Right
sifa	Numeric	8	2	Št. člana gospod.	None	None	8	Right
ank	Numeric	8	2	Val anketiranja	(1,00, 1 val)	None	8	Right
refced	Numeric	8	2	Št. člana gospo.	None	None	8	Right
v1	Numeric	8	2	Val anketiranja	(2,00, teren..)	None	8	Right
datum	Numeric	8	2	Datum anketira.	None	None	8	Right
starost	Numeric	8	2	Starost anketir.	None	None	8	Right
ank	Numeric	8	2	Št. članke	None	None	8	Right
refced	Numeric	8	2	Referenčni tedni	None	None	8	Right
v1_1	Numeric	8	2	Ali bo oseba od.	(1,00, Da)	None	8	Right
v1_4	Numeric	8	2	Razmerja med ..	(1,00, njego..)	None	8	Right
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v1_6	Numeric	8	2	Njegovih oča ..	(1,00, otrok a..)	None	8	Right
v1_7	Numeric	8	2	Njegova/ena ..	(1,00, otrok a..)	None	8	Right
v1_8	Numeric	8	2	Spol	(1,00, mešč..)	None	8	Right
v1_9a	Numeric	8	2	Dan rojstva	None	None	8	Right
v1_9c	Numeric	8	2	Mesec rojstva	None	None	8	Right
v1_10	Numeric	8	2	Leto rojstva	None	None	8	Right
v1_11a	Numeric	8	2	Ali imate sloven.	(1,00, Da)	None	8	Right
v1_12	Numeric	8	2	Ali ste bili rojen.	(1,00, Da)	None	8	Right
v1_13a	Numeric	8	2	V kateri državi	(2,00, Se n..)	None	8	Right
v1_14	Numeric	8	2	Kateroga leta s.	(1,00, Omo..)	None	8	Right
v1_15a	Numeric	8	2	Iz katere države.	(1,00, Omo..)	None	8	Right
v1_16	Numeric	8	2	Ali imate na te.	(1,00, stah..)	None	8	Right
v1_17	Numeric	8	2	Kakšen je vaš.	(1,00, Sams..)	None	8	Right
v2_1	Numeric	8	2	Vaša dosežena.	(1,00, ste br..)	None	8	Right
v2_2a	Numeric	8	2	Kaj ste po izbor.	(None, None..)	None	8	Right
v1_13a_2	Numeric	8	2	Kateroga leta s.	(None, None..)	None	8	Right
v1_14	Numeric	8	2	Ali ste v zadnji.	(1,00, Da)	None	8	Right
v1_15a	Numeric	8	2	Katero stopnja.	(1,00, Omo..)	None	8	Right
v1_16	Numeric	8	2	Ali ste v zadnji.	(1,00, Da)	None	8	Right
v1_17	Numeric	8	2	Koliko ur ste v.	(None, None..)	None	8	Right
v2_1	Numeric	8	2	Tačaj, seminar.	(1,00, potre..)	None	8	Right
v2_2	Numeric	8	2	Tajnik, strokov.	(1,00, potre..)	None	8	Right

Vprašanje	Presek
1.1. Vrtilnik članov gospodinjstva	
1.2. Imena članov gospodinjstva	
SAMO ZA PONOVLJENO ANKETIRANJE	
1.3. Kje živi oseba?	
1. V katero državo ste prišli v Slovenijo?	brez
2. V katero državo ste prišli v Slovenijo?	brez
3. Na katere države v Sloveniji?	brez
4. V kateri državi?	brez
5. Iz katere države ste prišli v Slovenijo?	brez
6. Iz katere države ste prišli v Slovenijo?	brez
1.4. Katero leto ste se preselili v Slovenijo?	
1.4.1. Katero leto ste se preselili v Slovenijo?	
1.4.2. Katero leto ste se preselili v Slovenijo?	
1.4.3. Katero leto ste se preselili v Slovenijo?	
1.4.4. Katero leto ste se preselili v Slovenijo?	
1.5. Spol	
1.6. Ali imate slovensko državljanstvo?	7,1%
1.7. Državljanstvo katere države imate?	
1.8. Ali ste bili rojeni v Sloveniji?	6,1%
1.9. V kateri državi ste bili rojeni?	
1.10. Kateroga leta ste se prvič prišli v Slovenijo?	
1.11. Ali imate na tem mestu stalno prebivališče, stalno prebivališče ali na njem nimate prebivališča?	
1.12. Datum rojstva	
1.13. Kakšen je vaš zakoniti stan?	

Preparing Public Use Files – the purpose of it

- no new SORS microdata have been in the last years distributed by ADP, the newest ones on our webpage are Census 2002 microdata
- one of our target groups, undergraduate students, is not familiar with SORS microdata (can't access them in the detailed form), so they are not aware of the advantages of using them
- the majority of researchers would benefit from a simpler access to moderately anonymized microdata
- the developed anonymization procedure keeps as much statistical information intact as possible, data are of sufficient quality to be used for advanced level of research

Preparing Public Use Files – how we do it

- in cooperation with SORS Sector for General Methodology and Standards
- anonymisation procedure which follows Eurostat LFS anonymisation criteria (in SPSS)
- calculating individual and global risk (R! – sdcMicro)
- calculating strata allocation, based on individual risk averages by strata (R! – bethel)
- stratified sampling, based on the inclusion probability of a certain case (R! – sampling – samplecube)
- sample weights recalculation

Preparing Public Use Files – evaluation of methods

- additionally, the comparison of anonymisation methods, software and technics to improve the anonymisation process in terms of complexity and time used, is in progress
- as the responsible employees at the Slovenian NSI don't have much time to concentrate on preparing PUF, we would like to optimize the process and keep the quality of PUF data
- comparison of methods and technics used by open-source software
- data reduction techniques, data perturbation techniques, sampling, generating synthetic microdata
- R! - sdcMicro package (bethel and sampling), The Cornell Anonymization Toolkit, μ -ARGUS, open-source synthetic data generator

METADATA - metadata harvesting from SORS systems

- the analysis of SORS metadata systems and other possible metadata sources was made
- METIS metadata standard had been introduced in the past, but the remains of the system couldn't be used for automatic harvesting of sufficient metadata
- some bits and pieces of metadata could be, on the other hand, harvested from some databases, applications, e-versions of documentation (quality reports, methodological explanations, databases, questionnaires etc.)
- since all this is saved in different systems, several employees from different SORS departments should consequently be involved in the metadata preparation process – automatic harvesting of all metadata researchers need is not possible

METADATA – metadata standard counseling

- SORS is working on improvements of its microdata and metadata documentation systems
- Social Science Data Archives have extensive experience with DDI standard
- in the process of analyzing the possibilities of (semi)automatic metadata harvesting, ADP and SORS got some useful information, applicable for working on both documentation projects in the future
- internal presentation on the ADP processes of long term preservation and metadata standard used was given
- ADP counsels and advices SORS work groups on metadata standards

METADATA – structured metadata for researchers

- DDI standard is used
- study descriptions are being prepared, ADP DDI extended scheme is used – including methodological, file description, data description, publication, other material etc. metadata fields
- all the required/useful documentation is made available to researchers in one place (codebooks, questionnaires, publications, syntaxes, methodological explanations etc.)
- metadata is being harvested from SORS and EUROSTAT documentation and websites, also by contacting separate SORS departments, responsible for conducting a survey

Availability of prepared metadata – ADP website

The navigation bar features the Social Science Data Archives logo on the left, followed by three main menu categories: Data (Search, Content fields, Series), User support (About data, Training, Depositing data, About archiving), and Community (Record study, Contribute data, Contribute materials, Blog, Projects). On the far left, there are icons for a home page, search, and social media links (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn).

Labour force survey, 2010: Annual data - no confidentiality restrictions

[Study description](#) | [Data description](#) | [Materials and publications](#) | [Download data](#)

ADP - IDNo: ADS10

Main author(s):

Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia

Data file producer:

SORS - *Statistični urad Republike Slovenije = Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia (Ljubljana, Slovenia; 2012)*

Funding agency:

(1):Based on the Law on National Statistics, all the activities, listed in the Annual Program of Statistical Surveys 2010, are financed by the National Budget of the Republic of Slovenia.

(2):European Commission with funds to be used for methodological improvements (occasionally).

Series:

- *ADS/Labour force survey*

Labour Force Survey is the biggest official statistics household survey in the Republic of Slovenia. A purpose of the survey is to collect information about current state and changes in employment and unemployment and economic inactivity in Slovene labour market. It provides data on the size, structure and characteristics of the active (employment and unemployed persons) and non-active population of Slovenia. Until 1995 the project was named Workforce survey. As the development project was launched at the Institute of Social Sciences at the Faculty of Social Sciences. The development phase lasted until the end of 1992. After 1993 it is part of Official National statistical research program. From that time on the data has an official status. From 1995 on Labour Force Survey is conducted under auspice of the Statistical office of the Republic of Slovenia. In years 1993 and 1994 the survey was held together by Employment office of Republic and the Statistical office of the Republic of Slovenia. Labour Force Survey is conducted in accordance with the instructions of International Labour Organization (ILO), adopted by the 13th Conference of Labour Statisticians, and in accordance with the requirements of the European Union Statistical Office (Eurostat), based on a harmonized survey of the European Union. Comparability of data with other countries and across time is thus

Complete study description

Access to data:

[study description](#) | [download data](#)

Status of the study: 4 - Full Study description and XML DDI Codebook Data description with full questions text.

9: highest range, comparative or continuous research, influential populations, with methodological excellence
Publication date: 2012

How to quote this study?

Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia. Labour force survey, 2010 [data file]. Slovenia, Ljubljana: Statistični urad Republike Slovenije = Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia [production, distribution], 2012. Slovenia, Ljubljana: Univerza v Ljubljani = University of Ljubljana, Arhiv družboslovnih podatkov = Social Science Data Archives [distribution], 2012.

Related studies:

- [AKP89 - Workforce survey 1989](#)
- [AKP91 - Workforce survey 1991](#)
- [AKP92 - Workforce survey 1992](#)
- [AKP93 - Workforce survey 1993](#)
- [AKP94 - Workforce survey 1994](#)

Availability of prepared metadata – Nesstar

adp arhiv družboslovnih podatkov

LEGENDA OPISA STOPNJE RAZISKAV:
1 POLNI OPIS RAZISKAVE
2 IN KODIRNA KNJIGA Z IMENI SPREMENLJIVK IZ PODATKOVNE DATOTEKE
3 IN KODIRNA KNJIGA Z IMENI SPREMENLJIVK S POLNIM BESEDILOM VPRAŠANJ

DESCRIPTION TABULATION

ADP
ADP-en
ADS - Labour Force Survey
[ADS]³ Labour force survey : Series information **NEW**
[AKP89]² Workforce survey 1989
[AKP91]² Workforce survey 1991
[AKP92]² Workforce survey 1992
[AKP93]² Workforce survey 1993
[AKP94]¹ Workforce survey 1994
[ADS95]² Labour force survey 1995
[ADS96]² Labour force survey 1996
[ADS972]³ Labour force survey, 1997/2
[ADS973]³ Labour force survey, 1997/3
[ADS974]³ Labour force survey, 1997/4
[ADS981]³ Labour force survey, 1998/1
[ADS982]³ Labour force survey, 1998/2
[ADS983]³ Labour force survey, 1998/3
[ADS984]³ Labour force survey, 1998/4
[ADS991]³ Labour force survey, 1999/1
[ADS992]³ Labour force survey, 1999/2
[ADS993]³ Labour force survey, 1999/3
[ADS994]³ Labour force survey, 1999/4
[ADS001]³ Labour force survey, 2000/1
[ADS002]³ Labour force survey, 2000/2
[ADS003]³ Labour force survey, 2000/3
[ADS004]³ Labour force survey, 2000/4
[ADS01]³ Labour force survey, 2001 : Annual data - no confidentiality restrictions **NEW**
[ADS02]³ Labour force survey, 2002 : Annual data - no confidentiality restrictions **NEW**
[ADS03]³ Labour force survey, 2003 : Annual data - no confidentiality restrictions **NEW**
[ADS04]³ Labour force survey, 2004 : Annual data - no confidentiality restrictions **NEW**
[ADS05]³ Labour force survey, 2005 : Annual data - no confidentiality restrictions **NEW**
[ADS06]³ Labour force survey, 2006 : Annual data - no confidentiality restrictions **NEW**
[ADS07]³ Labour force survey, 2007 : Annual data - no confidentiality restrictions **NEW**
[ADS08]³ Labour force survey, 2008 : Annual data - no confidentiality restrictions **NEW**
[ADS09]³ Labour force survey, 2009 : Annual data - no confidentiality restrictions **NEW**
[ADS10]³ Labour force survey, 2010 : Annual data - no confidentiality restrictions **NEW**
Metadata
Variable Description
Bookmarks
[ADS11]³ Labour force survey, 2011 : Annual data - no confidentiality restrictions **NEW**

Dataset: [ADS10]³ Labour force survey, 2010 : Annual data - no confidentiality restrictions

Full Title
[ADS10]³ Labour force survey, 2010 : Annual data - no confidentiality restrictions

Subtitle
Annual data - no confidentiality restrictions

Parallel Title
Anketa o delovni sili, 2010: Letna datoteka - brez omejitev zaupnosti

Identification Number
ads10-en

Authoring Entity

- Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia Affiliation: SORS

Producer

- Statistični urad Republike Slovenije = Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia Abbreviation: SORS

Date of Production
2012

Place of Production
Ljubljana, Slovenia

Funding Agency/Sponsor

- (1):Based on the Law on National Statistics, all the activities, listed in the Annual Program of Statistical Surveys 2010, are financed by the National Budget of the Republic of Slovenia. Grant: (1):Official Gazette of the Republic of Slovenia: 93/2009
- (2):European Commission with funds to be used for methodological improvements (occasionally). Grant: (1):Official Gazette of the Republic of Slovenia: 93/2009

Data Distributor

- Statistični urad Republike Slovenije = Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia , Arhiv družboslovnih podatkov = Social Science Data Archives

Contact Person

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Availability of prepared metadata – safe room, remote access

ads10_en_v1_r2.pdf - Adobe Reader

File Edit View Window Help

1 / 71 71,5%

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 - Other materials
 - Data description

ADP - IDNo: ADS10

Labour force survey, 2010: Annual data - no confidentiality restrictions

Anketa o delovni sili, 2010: Letna datoteka - brez omejitve zaupnosti

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Author(s):
SORS - Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia

Production of this document:
ADP - Social Science Data Archives, 2012

Data production:
SORS - Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia, 2012

Social Science Data Archives, 2013
1

Availability of prepared metadata – html browsing document

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the following elements:

- Address Bar:** S:\ARHIV 2\SHARED\prenosi_med_osebni\sebastian\Drugo\za_raziskovalce_var
- Page Title:** Index of surveys
- Navigation:** HOME, SL | EN
- Logos:** STATISTIČNI URAD REPUBLIKE SLOVENIJE (www.stat.si) and Social Science Data Archives.
- Section:** List of surveys
- Links:** Codebooks by year, Variable comparison by year
- Table:** A list of surveys from 2001 to 2008, each with three icons (pencil, document, and book) representing metadata options.

Survey Name	Metadata Icon 1	Metadata Icon 2	Metadata Icon 3
Labour Force Survey 2001			
Labour Force Survey 2002			
Labour Force Survey 2003			
Labour Force Survey 2004			
Labour Force Survey 2005			
Labour Force Survey 2006			
Labour Force Survey 2007			
Labour Force Survey 2008			

Availability of prepared metadata – html browsing document

HOME SL | EN

 STATISTIČNI URAD
REPUBLIKE SLOVENIJE
www.stat.si

 Social Science Data Archives

Instructions

The overview tool in front of you is prepared to be used for browsing metadata for the listed researches of the Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia. To access microdata you need the approval from the Data Protection Committee. Then you can use databases and conduct statistical analysis. The tool is prepared both in Slovene and English and the language can be changed by clicking on one of the desired languages on the button »SL | EN«.

Surveys are sorted by series. On the left side you can find a list of surveys with prepared metadata. You can select what metadata you would like to search by clicking on one of the buttons on the right side. The following information could be selected:

Codebooks used by year: The list of codebooks, available to researchers to clarify the values of individual variables, is presented by the year of conducting a Labour Force Survey. Codebooks used have changed between different periods of conducting a survey.

Variable comparison by year: The list of all variables of the Labour Force Survey is presented. Two separate lists are presented, from 2001 to 2004 and from 2005 to 2011, because of the major changes between the surveys LFS 2004 and LFS 2005. The document is meant to be used as a basis for building time series.

 Study description: The whole study description is available; DDI 2.0 metadata standard is used. The description includes a big spectrum of metadata, from the information on the author of a research to the information on collecting data and research documentation, required for a researcher to be able to use a database appropriately.

 Data description: Data on the variable level, frequencies or descriptive statistics, are presented. Variable values with low frequencies are hidden to protect privacy of a research respondent.

 Other documentation: The documentation, required for a researcher to be able to use databases efficiently, is presented. It includes questionnaires, explanatory notes, codebooks and important scientific publications as a result of a statistical analysis of the research data. The mentioned documentation could be easily accessed by clicking on the hyperlinks in the documents.

Promotional activities – channels used

- national conferences (Multiconference Information Society 2012, Statistical Days 2012, Joint Conference of Slovenian Sociological Association and ESA Working Group 2012)
- international conferences (IASSIST 2013, ESRA 2013, Applied Statistics 2013)
- ADP and Faculty of Social Sciences websites
- ADP social network sites (FB, Twitter), blog
- SORS website, to be renovated and the part about microdata access improved (ADP presented the researchers' point of view and suggested solutions)
- mailing lists (Slovenian Research Agency, SORS microdata users)
- national workshops for students and researchers

Results of the national cooperation

- Labour Force Survey 2001-2011 detailed deindividualized microdata, structured metadata, survey documentation gathered; available in the safe room or by the remote access
- Register data on public expenditures to support pensioners
- Labour Force Survey 2010 Public Use File
- html browsing document
- metadata system, analysis, harvesting, counseling, development
- becoming familiar with organizational policies, procedures, work specifics; working with different SORS departments; developing procedures, low input-high output model of cooperation

Challenges of the future

- preparing microdata and metadata of selected surveys, register data (including PUF)
- decision based on researchers' needs, importance, practicability and applicability of data, availability of SORS employees (Register Census 2011, EU SILC, CIS f.e.)
- continuation of work done (updates in a series)
- harvesting metadata from upgraded metadata and microdata documentation systems
- organizing workshops for students (LFS workshop in Autumn 2013)
- addressing researchers needs (what, where, how, in what form)

STATISTICAL OFFICE OF THE REPUBLIC OF SLOVENIA

DwB

Data without Boundaries

Social Science Data Archives

THANK YOU FOR YOUR ATTENTION!

Sebastian Kočar (Slovene Social Science Data Archives)

5th Conference of the European Survey Research Association – ESRA 2013

Ljubljana, Slovenia

July 2013